

**How is Economic Growth Impacted by the Neighbours and the
past? Can Tourism be an Alternative Engine of Economic
growth?**

Author:

Vítor João Pereira Domingues Martinho (vdmartinho@esav.ipv.pt)

- School of Agriculture (ESAV), Polytechnic Institute of Viseu (IPV), 3500-631 Viseu, Portugal

Abstract: The place and the time where we are influencing our lives, particularly our options, decisions and conditions to achieve the objectives planned. The same happens with the conditions for economic growth worldwide and the respective interrelationships with the competitiveness framework. The competitiveness is related to the conditions of the countries to have advantages in the international markets. It is influenced by several factors, where economic growth has an important contribution. The conditions for sustainable economic growth are well explained in the economic theory and literature, however not always in a consensual way, which opens the field for novel scientific inputs. Considering these contexts, this research aims to bring additional added value for the worldwide economic growth, namely how the past events and the neighbouring countries impact the worldwide economic dynamics and consequently the competitiveness conditions. Special emphasis was placed on tourism, given its global dynamics and its importance to the economy of some countries. To achieve these objectives data from the World Bank was considered. The period analysed was from 2016 to 2023, considering data from 2015 to 2023 to calculate growth rates for employment and output (gross domestic product). This statistical information was assessed considering the developments associated with the Kaldor laws and the spatial autocorrelation approaches (cross-section methodologies, following the procedures proposed by the software GeoDa). The results highlight that the impacts of recent international events remain for the subsequent years and each country is influenced by the conjunctures of the neighbours. On the other hand, the tourism sector is of major importance to the world's economic dynamics, but their impact depends on the

specifics of each circumstance and location. These are interesting insights to support policymakers in designing policies that are more adjusted to the current context, where the impacts of the past and of neighbouring countries cannot be ignored. The originality of this study lies in the use of extended Keynesian cross-section models with variables related to spatial effects and tourism to analyse the contexts associated with COVID-19. This is an approach whose results could serve as a basis for adjusting public policies.

Keywords: Kaldor law; spatial autocorrelation; cross-section regressions; Covid-19 pandemic; Russia-Ukraine conflict

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